

Singlet-Triplet Excited-State Inversion in Heptazine and Related Molecules: Assessment of TD-DFT and *ab initio* Methods

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Abstract

We have investigated the origin of the S_1 - T_1 energy levels inversion for heptazine and other N-doped π -conjugated hydrocarbons, leading thus to an unusually negative singlet-triplet energy gap ($\Delta E_{ST} < 0$). Since this inversion might rely on substantial doubly-excited configurations to the S_1 and T_1 wavefunctions, we have systematically applied multi-configurational CASSCF and NEVPT2 methods, SCS-corrected CC2 and ADC(2) approaches, and linear-response TD-DFT, to analyze if the latter approach could face this challenging issue. An intricate interplay between the singlet-triplet exchange interaction, the influence of doubly-excited configurations, and the impact of dynamic correlation effects, serves to explain the $\Delta E_{ST} < 0$ values found.

Key words: Singlet-triplet energy gap; heptazine derivatives; electron correlation effects; TD-DFT; CASSCF; NEVPT2; SCS-CC2; SCS-ADC(2).

1 Introduction

Heptazine (also commonly known as tri-*s*-triazine and composed of three fused triazine rings) consists on a triangular core with N-substituted sites and it was first synthesized in 1982.¹ There is now a renewed interest in heptazine derivatives as precursors of nitrogen-rich carbon nitrides,^{2,3} building blocks of photocatalytic porous polymer networks,^{4,5} and efficient light-emitters^{6,7} in Organic Light-Emitting Diodes (OLEDs), among other envisioned applications. Besides, and more generally speaking, nitrogen- and boron-doped triangulene-based compounds, such as DABNA-1 or TABNA,⁸⁻¹⁰ present unique features with high interest for optoelectronics applications, such as narrow emission and high quantum yield, while displaying Thermally Activated Delayed Fluorescence (TADF). These properties are driven by short-range charge-transfer, which spatially separate the hole and the electron densities on neighbouring atomic sites while ensuring a high polarizability.¹¹ Oligomerization of heptazine is also a promising and versatile route towards catalysis for hydrogen production and water splitting¹²⁻¹⁴ and CO₂ uptake,¹⁵ as well as substitution at the corners to improve the photocatalytic performance.¹⁶ This scenario allows to foresee a blooming of studies for energy conversion and storage, as well as for industrial and environmental applications of heptazine derivatives and oligomers.^{17,18}

Particularly interesting from both an experimental and theoretical point of view, e.g. in the search of more efficient photophysical applications,¹⁹ is the location of the lowest singlet and triplet excited-state energy levels of triangular shape molecules. Recent works have shown a violation of Hund's multiplicity rule in nitrogen-doped triangulenes, namely cyclazine and heptazine, with the lowest triplet excited-state (T_1) found higher in energy than

the lowest singlet excited-state (S_1) contrarily to almost all known closed-shell organic molecules.²⁰ Violation of Hund’s rule has been studied before, mostly for establishing the correct spin multiplicity of the ground-state,^{21,22} and it can occur for π -conjugated hydrocarbons with a bipartite lattice. The triangle-shaped topology of heptazine and related molecules could certainly play some role²³ but the importance of on-site heterosubstitution with N atoms, and how closely related molecules could obey or not the Hund’s rule, deserves to be further investigated to establish structure-property relationships.²⁴ We have thus selected a set of N-substituted hydrocarbons with a triangle-like shape, see Figure 1, and carefully applied state-of-the-art excited-state methods to obtain the desired energy levels.

The most probably used method to access excited-state energies; i.e., Time-Dependent Density-Functional Theory (TD-DFT),^{25–28} has been shown unable to provide for these molecules the correct order of the states, independently of the exchange-correlation functional selected. The global accuracy of TD-DFT is out of question, as well as its excellent trade-off between accuracy and computational cost for real-world applications, but there are also **some applications for which the adiabatic approximation might be problematic**. This is systematically explored here, inspecting first the corresponding theoretical expression in which the singlet-triplet gap is based. Additionally, we will try to provide insights, beyond the one-electron molecular picture,²⁹ to understand why highly correlated methods are able to cope with the underlying electronic structure of these systems, and thus predicting the correct order and energy of excited-states. This theoretical understanding could pave the way towards the theoretical design of other closed-shell organic molecules with inverted excited-states and therefore with

prospects in optoelectronic and photocatalytic applications.

2 Theoretical framework

2.1 Explicit expression from the TD-DFT method

One central aspect of the present work is to demonstrate if the inversion of S_1 and T_1 states can be predicted or not accurately by TD-DFT: we thus present first the explicit expression for the corresponding energy difference, ΔE_{ST} , to understand the origin of its performance. Upon a linear-response regime, the excitation energies (Ω) between ground- and excited-states arise from the solution of the non-Hermitian eigenvalue problem:³⁰

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{B}^* & \mathbf{A}^* \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{X} \\ \mathbf{Y} \end{bmatrix} = \Omega_{\text{TD-DFT}} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{1} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & -\mathbf{1} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{X} \\ \mathbf{Y} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

with \mathbf{X} (\mathbf{Y}) the set of (de-)excitation amplitudes. Occupied (unoccupied) orbitals are denoted in the following as i, j (a, b). We can introduce in the expression (if needed) the weight (C_x) of the HF-like exchange term entering into the hybrid form of the exchange-correlation hybrid functional, $E_{xc}[\rho]$, chosen. A pure (semi-local) functional will have consequently $C_x = 0$. The spinless matrix elements of the orbital rotation Hessians matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} are given by:

$$A_{ia,jb} = \delta_{ij}\delta_{ab}(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_i) + (ia|jb) - C_x(ij|ab) + (1 - C_x)(ia|\hat{f}_{xc}|jb) \quad (2)$$

$$B_{ia,jb} = (ia|bj) - C_x(ib|aj) + (1 - C_x)(ia|\hat{f}_{xc}|bj), \quad (3)$$

with ϵ the energy eigenvalue, $(ia|jb)$ the integral $\iint \phi_i^*(\mathbf{r})\phi_a(\mathbf{r})\frac{1}{|\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}'|}\phi_j^*(\mathbf{r}')\phi_b(\mathbf{r}')d\mathbf{r}d\mathbf{r}'$, which could take an exchange-type, $(ia|jb)$ or simply K , or as a Coulomb-type form, $(ij|ab)$; and $(ia|\hat{f}_{xc}|jb)$ the integral $\iint \phi_i^*(\mathbf{r})\phi_a(\mathbf{r})\hat{f}_{xc}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', \omega)\phi_j^*(\mathbf{r}')\phi_b(\mathbf{r}')d\mathbf{r}d\mathbf{r}'$, with $\hat{f}_{xc} = \frac{\delta^2 E_{xc}[\rho]}{\delta\rho(\mathbf{r})\delta\rho(\mathbf{r}')}$ the exchange-correlation kernel. Note that: (i) in the adiabatic approximation often used, \hat{f}_{xc} is made frequency-independent and

thus $\hat{f}_{xc}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$; and (ii) the term $(ia|\hat{f}_{xc}|bj)$ is negative definite³¹ with a magnitude depending on each system and the exchange-correlation functional chosen.

The Tamm-Dancoff approximation³² sets $\mathbf{B} = 0$ in the full TD-DFT equations; Eq. (1) thus becomes $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{X} = \Omega_{\text{TDA-DFT}}\mathbf{X}$, with the matrix elements simplified (setting also $C_x = 0$) to:

$$A_{ia,jb} = \delta_{ij}\delta_{ab}(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_i) + (ia|jb) + (ia|\hat{f}_{xc}|jb). \quad (4)$$

Note that: (i) in contrast to the Configuration Interaction Singles (CIS) formalism, any TD(A)-DFT result will also depend on the $(ia|\hat{f}_{xc}|jb)$ term; and (ii) the CIS method is recovered **by replacing the last term by $-(ij|ab)$** . Since our main interests is the singlet-triplet energy difference, **it thus becomes that:**

$$\Delta E_{ST} = 2(ia|jb) + 2(ia|\hat{f}_{xc}|jb). \quad (5)$$

Note that this result was previously emphasized on Refs. 11 and 33. For TDA-DFT, the second term in Eq. (5) is expected to decrease the ΔE_{ST} values, with potentially ΔE_{ST} being negative depending on the relative magnitude of $|(ia|\hat{f}_{xc}|jb)|$ vs. $(ia|jb)$, **since two-electron integral (first term) are positive definite.**

2.2 Computational details

All the structures were optimized by the B97-3c method³⁴ obtaining rigid and completely planar geometries with all-real $(3N - 6)$ vibrational frequencies. Then, we calculated (vertical) relative energies between ground- and lowest excited-state of singlet (S_1) and triplet (T_1) multiplicity, $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$

and $T_1 \leftarrow S_0$ respectively, giving rise to the singlet-triplet energy difference always calculated as $\Delta E_{ST} = E(S_1 \leftarrow S_0) - E(T_1 \leftarrow S_0)$. Relaxing the geometrical structures of the S_1 and T_1 states is not expected to have any influence due to the rigidity of the molecular backbone.¹⁹ We carried out Time-Dependent DFT calculations (TD-DFT) together with the Tamm-Dancoff approximation (TDA-DFT),³² with PBE-based exchange-correlation functionals.^{35,36} However, the conclusions are not expected to differ upon employing any other approximation (e.g. the M06-2X³⁷ and ω B97XD functionals³⁸ are also explored). The multi-configurational Complete Active Space Self-Consistent Field (State-Averaged) (SA-)CASSCF and N-electron Valence second-order Perturbation Theory (Strongly-Contracted) (SC-)NEVPT2³⁹⁻⁴¹ methods employed an increasingly larger (N, M) active space of N electrons in M orbitals, and demanded the same number of roots of each multiplicity (S_n and T_n). To be sure that the results remain independent of the method selected, we also performed other *ab initio* calculations: (i) Configuration Interaction Singles, CIS, also approximately corrected with Double excitations, CIS(D); (ii) Second-order approximate Coupled Cluster singles and doubles model, CC2;^{42,43} and (iii) Second-order Algebraic Diagrammatic Construction, ADC(2).⁴⁴ Note that for CC2 and ADC(2) the Spin-Component-Scaling (SCS-) correction was employed⁴⁵ to account for missing correlation effects upon scaling the same and opposite spin-components separately. The TDA-DFT, CIS, SA-CASSCF, and SC-NEVPT2 calculations are done with the ORCA 4.0 package;⁴⁶ CIS(D), SCS-CC2, and SCS-ADC(2) are instead done with the TURBOMOLE 7.4 package.⁴⁷ We fixed the def2-TZVP basis set⁴⁸ for all the calculations, which were done with the Resolution-of-the-Identity (RI) approximation,⁴⁹ together with the corresponding auxiliary basis sets⁵⁰ def2/JK and def2-TZVP/C.

2.3 Previous evidences of $\Delta E_{ST} < 0$ for heptazine and its derivatives

Next, we will summarize the available experimental and theoretical information about these systems. Recent experimental studies on heptazine (actually a substituted heptazine but with substituents attached to the corners weakly affecting its electronic structure and photophysics) clearly evidenced the inversion of S_1 and T_1 states²⁰ from the observed long lifetime of the S_1 state in presence or in absence of molecular oxygen which is expected to quench triplet excited states. Prompt and delayed fluorescence has been also demonstrated on several heptazine derivatives.⁵¹ Note also that the absorption spectra of 2T-N and 2T-4N were also measured in the past,^{52,53} with the energy location of the triplet state being still challenging. Actually, it was also experimentally found a very short lifetime of the T_1 state of 2T-4N,⁵³ compatible with a radiationless intersystem crossing $S_1 \leftarrow T_1$ and thus isoenergetic energy levels. From a theoretical point of view, previous estimates of ΔE_{ST} at different sophisticated theoretical levels such as RAS-SF, ADC(2), and EOM-CCSD predicted values between -0.10 and -0.16 eV for 2T-N,^{33,54} while ADC(2), CC2, EOM-CCSD, and CASPT2 methods predicted ΔE_{ST} energies between -0.18 and -0.28 eV for 2T-7N.²⁰

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Understanding the performance of the TD-DFT method

To quantitatively corroborate the arguments exposed above about the (possible) inability of CIS and TDA-DFT methods to predict a $\Delta E_{ST} < 0$ value for these systems, a preliminary calculation of ΔE_{ST} by CIS for the

three compounds selected, see Table 1, leads to:

$$\Delta E_{ST}^{\text{CIS}}(2\text{T-N}) = 0.337 \text{ eV} \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta E_{ST}^{\text{CIS}}(2\text{T-4N}) = 0.685 \text{ eV} \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta E_{ST}^{\text{CIS}}(2\text{T-7N}) = 0.410 \text{ eV}. \quad (8)$$

In the simplest “two-state” model, see Ref. 24 for details, that would lead to a value of K , often referred as the “exchange energy” comprised between 0.17 – 0.34 eV, and thus slightly smaller than the values of around 0.4–0.5 eV commonly found in π -conjugated polymers.⁵⁵ However, that is a rough approximation for K only valid for a model with singlet and triplet states sharing the same electron configuration but different spin. For a more robust expression, as that arising from a more extended “four-state” model see also Ref. 24. These small values (**in a simplified view**) are believed to arise from a minor overlap between the frontier occupied and virtual orbitals and helped to explain, for instance, former strategies to decrease the ΔE_{ST} values by relying on the Donor-Acceptor (D-A) fragment strategy,⁵⁶ of interest for the field of organic light-emission.⁵⁷ Actually, Figure 2 presents the disjoint nature of both the Highest Occupied and Lowest Unoccupied Molecular Orbitals (HOMO and LUMO) for this set of compounds, easily seen the different spatial location of the lobes and their expected poor overlap.

If one performs a TDA-DFT calculation with just the PBE exchange functional, thus neglecting ($\hat{f}_c = 0$) the corresponding correlation functional,

we obtain:

$$\Delta E_{ST}^{\text{TDA-PBEx}}(2\text{T-N}) = 0.195 \text{ eV} \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta E_{ST}^{\text{TDA-PBEx}}(2\text{T-4N}) = 0.274 \text{ eV} \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta E_{ST}^{\text{TDA-PBEx}}(2\text{T-7N}) = 0.202 \text{ eV}, \quad (11)$$

while if we perform now the the corresponding TDA-DFT calculation, including now both PBE exchange and correlation terms:

$$\Delta E_{ST}^{\text{TDA-PBE}}(2\text{T-N}) = 0.187 \text{ eV} \quad (12)$$

$$\Delta E_{ST}^{\text{TDA-PBE}}(2\text{T-4N}) = 0.260 \text{ eV} \quad (13)$$

$$\Delta E_{ST}^{\text{TDA-PBE}}(2\text{T-7N}) = 0.199 \text{ eV}, \quad (14)$$

confirming these results the minor effect of the correlation potential, and kernel, for Kohn-Sham (KS) orbital shapes and energies,^{58,59} although in the correct direction of decreasing the singlet-triplet gap. Note that for other dyes commonly employed in the TADF field (i.e., 2CzPN, ACRXTN, DABNA-1, and TABNA) these conclusions remain, with variations of less than 0.1 eV for ΔE_{ST} between TDA-PBEx and TDA-PBE, showing how this is indeed a general performance.

This is further corroborated by the HF-PBE calculation (i.e., within a TDA-DFT framework adding the PBE correlation functional to the full Hartree-Fock-like or exact-exchange term) from which we obtain rather similar values to CIS:

$$\Delta E_{ST}^{\text{TDA-HF-PBE}}(2\text{T-N}) = 0.321 \text{ eV} \quad (15)$$

$$\Delta E_{ST}^{\text{TDA-HF-PBE}}(2\text{T-4N}) = 0.648 \text{ eV} \quad (16)$$

$$\Delta E_{ST}^{\text{TDA-HF-PBE}}(2\text{T-7N}) = 0.390 \text{ eV}. \quad (17)$$

Comparing now the results from Eqs. (6)-(8) and (12)-(14), we can observe the (negative) sign and magnitude (approximately half of the “exchange energy”) of the $(ia|\hat{f}_{xc}|jb)$ term,⁶⁰ although still leading to $\Delta E_{ST} > 0$ values. The use of a hybrid functional like PBE0 ($C_x = 1/4$) would just situate the ΔE_{ST} results between both extremes (i.e., CIS and TDA-PBE), as already found here and in previous publications too:³³ e.g. $\Delta E_{ST}^{\text{TDA-PBE0}}(2\text{T-N}) = 0.219$ eV. The use of a higher weight (i.e., $C_x = 0.54$ for M06-2X³⁷) does not bring any significant difference: $\Delta E_{ST}^{\text{TDA-M06-2X}}(2\text{T-N}) = 0.195$ eV. Due to the disjoint nature of HOMO and LUMO, and since excited states are mostly HOMO to LUMO excitations in the single-excitation picture, these excitations could thus be viewed as intramolecular (short-range) charge-transfer excitations similarly as for DABNA-1 and TABNA compounds. Previous failures of TD-DFT for dealing with charge-transfer excitations were corrected using a long-range correction to the $E_{xc}[\rho]$ functional, with the ωB97XD model³⁸ one of the most successfully employed versions. However, to discard that the wrong prediction of the $\Delta E_{ST} < 0$ values is not a question of short- vs. long-range effects of the exchange-correlation potential, the application of this functional to e.g. 2T-7N in previous publications²⁰ also led to a positive $\Delta E_{ST}^{\text{TDA-}\omega\text{B97XD}}(2\text{T-7N}) = 0.23$ eV. **In summary, it seems problematic to obtain a $\Delta E_{ST} < 0$ value with frequency-independent kernels.**⁶¹

3.2 Single- and Multi-reference ab initio results

We first start with the simplest CIS(D) method, with double excitations partly included through the (D) correction,⁶² which should allow to quantify the importance of this correction if so. Actually, the trend is completely reversed with respect to CIS, see Table 1, significantly modifying $\Delta E_{ST}^{\text{CIS}}$ by

-0.62, -0.98, and -0.93 eV, for 2T-N, 2T-4N, and 2T-7N, leading respectively to new values of:

$$\Delta E_{ST}^{\text{CIS(D)}}(2\text{T-N}) = -0.280 \text{ eV} \quad (18)$$

$$\Delta E_{ST}^{\text{CIS(D)}}(2\text{T-4N}) = -0.288 \text{ eV} \quad (19)$$

$$\Delta E_{ST}^{\text{CIS(D)}}(2\text{T-7N}) = -0.523 \text{ eV}. \quad (20)$$

The effect of double excitations for individual excited-state S_1 and T_1 energies is much more pronounced for S_1 , with a rough decrease (stabilization) of -42 %, -35 %, and -38 %, for 2T-N, 2T-4N, and 2T-7N, respectively, compared with the corresponding values for T_1 of -7 %, -5 %, and -20 %, in agreement with previous studies.⁶³ However, the ΔE_{ST} values at the CIS(D) should be taken with some caution from recent benchmark studies in organic chromophores.⁶⁴

Therefore, we systematically assess the impact of high-order excitations by considering next **some of the** correlated methods **applicable to excited-states** such as SCS-CC2, SCS-ADC(2), SA-CASSCF, and SCNEVPT2 to tackle these challenging systems. First of all, Table 1 also includes the results of the SCS-CC2 and SCS-ADC(2) methods, from which it can be consistently observe $\Delta E_{ST} < 0$ values. Since CCS results, Coupled-Cluster with Single excitations, are similar to CIS, the introduction of double excitations by CC2 is again key to have those results. Note also that CIS(D) and SCS-corrected CC2 or ADC(2) methods rely on rather different theories and approximations, but individual $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ and $T_1 \leftarrow S_0$ excitation energies are found in all cases in an excellent agreement between them, and with respect to the available experimental information. **Looking at the D_1 diagnostics⁶⁵ at the CC2 level, we found values around 0.08 for the three systems, and thus slightly higher than the threshold**

$D_1 \leq 0.05$ for which accurate results with respect to higher-order correlation methods are expected. However, we also observe a close agreement between the CC2-based results and those values previously calculated at the EOM-CCSD level for 2T-N (1.09 and 1.19 eV, respectively³³) and for 2T-7N (2.78 and 2.96 eV, respectively²⁰).

Table 2 reports the results of systematically applying SA-CASSCF and SC-NEVPT2 methods, with different active spaces to disentangle its effect (if any) on the results. The SA-CASSCF method sometimes leads to $\Delta E_{ST} > 0$ (i.e., for 2T-7N) and sometimes to $\Delta E_{ST} < 0$ (i.e., for 2T-N and 2T-4N) values, indicating that the introduction of non-dynamical correlation effects is not enough (although a first step) to deal with the intricate electronic effects of triangle-shaped systems due to its (partially) radical nature.⁵⁴ Contrarily to 2T-N and 2T-4N systems, the CASSCF results for $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ and $T_1 \leftarrow S_0$ excitation energies of 2T-7N are largely overestimated, with the NEVPT2 correction significantly decreasing the former (latter) excitation energies by 2.0–2.2 eV (1.1–1.3 eV). Looking at the radicaloid nature of the ground-state (S_0) of these systems, as given by the integrated number of electrons (N_U) housed on fractionally occupied orbitals,^{66–68} see details at the Supporting Information, we can see a transition from moderately (mono)radicaloid ($N_U = 0.75$ for 2T-N) to negligibly radicaloid ($N_U = 0.26$ character for 2T-7N), passing through an intermediate value of $N_U = 0.37$ character for 2T-4N.

Interestingly, when the dynamical correlation energy is introduced by the SC-NEVPT2 method, a value of $\Delta E_{ST} < 0$ for the singlet-triplet energy gap of all the systems is consistently obtained, in agreement with experimental

and other theoretical findings. Note also the quantitative agreement for individual $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ and $T_1 \leftarrow S_0$ excitation energies between NEVPT2 values and experimental estimates, a fact also corroborated before from benchmark calculations (pseudo-FCI results) of small systems.⁶⁹ This behaviour reflects the strong influence of “dynamic” correlation effects, introduced by the NEVPT2 method, for achieving a $\Delta E_{ST} < 0$ value for 2T-7N. **Furthermore, we also comment on the calculated $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ oscillator strengths, for which negligible values are observed (e.g. as much as $5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ at the NEVPT2(10,10) level for 2T-4N) in all cases and at all levels, leading essentially to dark states.**

We investigate the weight of double- and higher-order excitations in the final CAS wavefunction of these systems. The CAS wavefunction is expressed as a linear combination of simply-, doubly-, triply-substituted, etc. Slater determinants, but with the excitation operator confined within the subset of the selected active orbitals, as:

$$|\Psi_{\text{CAS}}\rangle = \sum_M C_M |\Psi_M\rangle = C_0 |\Psi_0\rangle + \sum_{i,a} C_i^a |\Psi_i^a\rangle + \sum_{ij,ab} C_{ij}^{ab} |\Psi_{ij}^{ab}\rangle + \sum_{ijk,abc} C_{ijk}^{abc} |\Psi_{ijk}^{abc}\rangle + \dots, \quad (21)$$

with C_i^a , C_{ij}^{ab} , C_{ijk}^{abc} , etc. the corresponding coefficients of the expansion. The relative weight of the sum of C_{ij}^{ab} , C_{ijk}^{abc} , etc. coefficients reflects the importance of n -tuple excitations beyond single-particle ones. Note that for the S_0 wavefunction of all the systems, values of 5.5 %, 3.8 %, and 1.0 %, for 2T-N, 2T-4N, and 2T-7N, are calculated, respectively, which correlates with the trend in the N_U values obtained.

Those weights are equal to 9.8 % (8.4 %) for the S_1 (T_1) excited-states of 2T-N, considerably higher than for other chromophores largely exploited

as light-emitters for TADF applications.⁷⁰ For instance, for the compound 2CzPN, for which a $\Delta E_{ST} > 0$ value is theoretically and experimentally obtained, those weights are 1.0 % and 0.7 %, respectively, at the SA-CASSCF level. Similarly for 2T-4N, we found values up to 9.5 % (8.0 %) for the S_1 (T_1) excited-states, and thus also slightly higher for the singlet than for the triplet wavefunction. Doubly-excited configurations are known to lead to a stabilization few times larger for singlet than for triplet excited-states, which supports the $\Delta E_{ST} < 0$ values obtained for 2T-N and 2T-4N essentially because Coulomb correlation primarily involves the interaction between anti-parallel spins.^{71,72} In strong contrast, for 2T-7N, those values are 0.0 % (2.5 %) for the S_1 (T_1) excited-states, and therefore substantially lower than for 2T-N and 2T-4N. The origin of the singlet-triplet inversion in 2T-7N is thus neither exclusively a small “exchange integral”, or at least not as smaller as that for 2T-N, nor a significant contribution of double excitations in the S_1 excited-state wavefunctions, or at least less significant than for 2T-N and 2T-4N but a rather strong *a posteriori* dynamical correction.

3.3 Extension to other systems

We first explore the dicarboxylate derivative of 2T-N, see Figure 1, namely 2T-N/CO₂H, for which experimental results are also available.⁵² For this case, $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ and $T_1 \leftarrow S_0$ experimental excitation energies are 1.07 and < 1.16 eV, respectively, leading again to a very small ΔE_{ST} value compatible with an inversion of the S_1 and T_1 states as it happened for 2T-N. Note that similar experimental results were found for monocarboxylate and nitrile derivatives of 2T-N, thus we will concentrate on the former molecule. Attaching the substituents did not significantly decrease the $N_U = 0.62$

value with respect to 2T-N, since the zig-zag edges housing reactive CH sites are not completely passivated.⁷³ We also obtain now $\Delta E_{ST} > 0$ values at all the TD-DFT levels, e.g. 0.22 eV at the TD-PBE0/def2-TZVP level, and $\Delta E_{ST} < 0$ values when NEVPT2, SCS-CC2, or SCS-ADC(2) methods are instead employed.

4 Conclusions

We have studied the energy order of the lowest singlet S_1 and triplet T_1 excited-states of a set of N-doped (triangular shape) π -conjugated hydrocarbons. The S_1 - T_1 gap (referred as ΔE_{ST}) of these systems is expected to be negative, thus promoting exogernic reverse intersystem crossing processes, of interest within the Organic Electronics field where spin statistics still limit the efficiencies of OLEDs devices.

Applying TD(A)-DFT, and independently of the exchange-correlation functional chosen, the S_1 - T_1 gap is always found positive. We have, quantitatively and step by step, demonstrated that: (i) the correlation contribution is very small for both terms entering into the analytical expression for ΔE_{ST} ; and (ii) the term $(ia|\hat{f}_{xc}|jb)$ is negative **compared to** the positive $(ia|jb)$ value, which still leads to $\Delta E_{ST} > 0$ values. **Values of $\Delta E_{ST} < 0$ are not expected to reach due to the adiabatic approximation employed in common applications of TD(A)-DFT.**

On the other hand, all the correlated *ab initio* methods, including CIS(D), SCS-CC2, SCS-ADC(2), SA-CASSCF, and SC-NEVPT2, led to $\Delta E_{ST} < 0$ values, with the exception of CIS. The systematic investigation performed

could isolate double (n -tuple) excitations, or more in general strong correlation effects, as key for correctly describing the S_1 and T_1 excited-states of 2T-N, 2T-4N, and 2T-7N. Nevertheless, this finding does not contradict the common strategy followed for D-A compounds, relying on $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ and $T_1 \leftarrow S_0$ intramolecular charge-transfer excitations, to achieve reduced ΔE_{ST} values. Actually, a pre-requisite for the S_1 - T_1 inversion is to minimize the exchange energy, since then the greater stabilization of the S_1 than the T_1 excited-state by double excitations would allow to achieve the desired $\Delta E_{ST} < 0$ values.

The case of 2T-7N (or heptazine) is particularly intriguing, in the sense that the S_1 excited-state is not longer influenced by doubly-excited configurations in the CAS wavefunction. However, strong correlation effects are also at the origin of its $\Delta E_{ST} < 0$ value, which can be seen by the wrong (right) prediction made by SA-CASSCF (SC-NEVPT2) calculations indicating negligible (pronounced) static (dynamic) correlation. This is also related with the number of unpaired electrons (N_U values) obtained, from which a smooth transition from moderate (2T-N) to small (2T-7N) radicaloid character of the ground-state is also obtained, correlated with a lower weight of n -tuple excitations in the CAS wavefunction of S_0 too.

In summary, we have shown both analytically and numerically, and by a variety of state-of-the-art methods for excited-states, the importance of electron correlation effects to predict the S_1 - T_1 inversion in N-doped (triangular shape) π -conjugated hydrocarbons. These conclusion could stimulate further studies of compounds giving rise to $\Delta E_{ST} < 0$ values, of relevance to photoactive materials, with carefully chosen electronic structure methods

guiding their theoretical design.

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Data Availability

The data that supports the findings of this study are available within the article [and its supplementary material] or are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Supplementary Material

The Supplementary Material contains in this order: (i) Individual $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ and $T_1 \leftarrow S_0$ excitation energies at the TD-DFT level; (ii) Description of the FT-DFT method used to obtain the N_U values; and (iii) Optimized cartesian coordinates of the compounds.

Table 1: Vertical excitation energies ($S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ and $T_1 \leftarrow S_0$, in eV) and associated singlet-triplet energy gap (ΔE_{ST}) calculated with different methods (and the def2-TZVP basis set) for N-doped compounds.

Molecule	Method	$S_1 \leftarrow S_0$	$T_1 \leftarrow S_0$	ΔE_{ST}
2T-N	CIS	1.797	1.460	0.337
	CIS(D)	1.042	1.322	-0.280
	SCS-CC2	1.110	1.334	-0.224
	SCS-ADC(2)	1.080	1.308	-0.228
	Exp. ^a	0.97	0.93	0.04
2T-4N	CIS	3.211	2.526	0.685
	CIS(D)	2.106	2.394	-0.288
	SCS-CC2	2.258	2.342	-0.084
	SCS-ADC(2)	2.125	2.303	-0.178
	Exp. ^b	<2.39	2.29	<0.10
2T-7N	CIS	4.328	3.918	0.410
	CIS(D)	2.627	3.150	-0.523
	SCS-CC2	2.847	3.226	-0.379
	SCS-ADC(2)	2.790	3.174	-0.384
	Exp. ^c	-	-	<0

^a Taken from Ref. 52.

^b Taken from Ref. 53.

^c Taken from Ref. 20.

Table 2: Vertical excitation energies ($S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ and $T_1 \leftarrow S_0$, in eV) and associated singlet-triplet energy gap (ΔE_{ST}) calculated with different methods (and the def2-TZVP basis set) for N-doped compounds.

Molecule	Method	$S_1 \leftarrow S_0$	$T_1 \leftarrow S_0$	ΔE_{ST}
2T-N	CASSCF(6,6)	0.826	0.936	-0.110
	CASSCF(8,8)	1.042	1.065	-0.023
	CASSCF(10,10)	0.773	0.949	-0.176
	NEVPT2(6,6)	1.107	1.259	-0.152
	NEVPT2(8,8)	1.010	1.152	-0.142
	NEVPT2(10,10)	1.127	1.192	-0.065
	Exp. ^a	0.97	0.93	0.04
2T-4N	CASSCF(6,6)	2.135	2.151	-0.016
	CASSCF(8,8)	2.455	2.176	0.279
	CASSCF(10,10)	2.136	2.110	0.026
	NEVPT2(6,6)	2.141	2.193	-0.052
	NEVPT2(8,8)	2.011	2.093	-0.082
	NEVPT2(10,10)	2.166	2.182	-0.016
	Exp. ^b	<2.39	2.29	<0.10
2T-7N	CASSCF(6,6)	4.395	3.962	0.433
	CASSCF(8,8)	4.406	3.949	0.457
	CASSCF(10,10)	4.467	4.019	0.448
	NEVPT2(6,6)	2.171	2.716	-0.545
	NEVPT2(8,8)	2.280	2.737	-0.457
	NEVPT2(10,10)	2.478	2.764	-0.286
	Exp. ^c	-	-	<0

^a Taken from Ref. 52.

^b Taken from Ref. 53.

^c Taken from Ref. 20.

Figure 1: Chemical structure of studied molecules (from top to bottom and from left to right): 2T-N (or cyclazine), 2T-4N, 2T-7N (or heptazine), and a substituted 2T-N namely 2T-N/CO₂H. Note that 2T refers to the number of hexagons per side, always forming a triangular shape molecule, and xN the number of N atoms substituting C sites.

Figure 2: Isocontour plots ($\sigma = 0.005 \text{ e/bohr}^3$) of HOMO (top) and LUMO (bottom) orbitals of 2T-N, 2T-4N, and 2T-7N, calculated at the HF/def2-TZVP level.

Figure 3: Chemical structure of studied molecules: 2T-B, 2T-4B, and 2T-7B. Note that 2T refers to the number of hexagons per side, always forming a triangular shape molecule, and xN the number of atoms substituting C sites.

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